

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL FOR ARTICLE: Effects of atrial fibrillation screening according to thyroid function: Post-hoc analysis of the randomized LOOP study

Short title: AF screening according to TSH

Authors and affiliations:

Daniel Camillo SPONA, BSc.Med^a, Diana My FRODI, MD^a, Lucas Yixi XING, MD^a, Emilie Katrine KONGEBRO, MD^a, Ketil Jørgen HAUGAN, MD, PhD^b, Claus GRAFF, PhD^c, Søren HØJBERG, MD, PhD^d, Derk KRIEGER, MD, PhD^e, Axel BRANDES, MD, DMSc^{f,g,h}, Lars KØBER, MD, DMSc^{a,i}, Morten S OLESEN, MSc, PhD^j, Andreas ANDERSEN, MD, PhD^k, Sofie HÆDESDAL MD, PhD^k, Ruth FRIKKE-SCHMIDT MD, PhD, DMSc^{m,i}, Jesper Hastrup SVENDSEN, MD, DMSc^{a,i*}, Søren Zöga DIEDERICHSEN, MD, PhD^{a*}

^a Department of Cardiology, Copenhagen University Hospital – Rigshospitalet
Inge Lehmanns Vej 7, 2100 Copenhagen, DENMARK

^b Department of Cardiology, Zealand University Hospital Roskilde
Sygehusvej 10, 4000 Roskilde DENMARK

^c Department of Health Science and Technology, Aalborg University
Selma Lagerlöfs Vej 249, 9260 Gistrup, DENMARK

^d Department of Cardiology, Copenhagen University Hospital – Bispebjerg
Bispebjerg Bakke 23, 2400 Copenhagen DENMARK

^e Stroke Unit, Medielinic City Hospital
Building 37 - 26th St, Dubai, UAE

^f Department of Cardiology, Odense University Hospital
J. B. Winsløvs Vej 4, 5000 Odense, DENMARK

^g Department of Regional Health Research, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Southern Denmark
Finsensgade 35, 6700 Esbjerg, DENMARK

^h Department of Cardiology, Esbjerg Hospital – University Hospital of Southern Denmark,
Finsensgade 35, 6700 Esbjerg, Denmark

ⁱ Department of Clinical Medicine, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen
Blegdamsvej 3B, 2200 Copenhagen, DENMARK

^j Department of Biomedical Sciences, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark
Blegdamsvej 3B, 2200 Copenhagen, DENMARK

^k Clinical Research, Copenhagen University Hospital – Steno Diabetes Center Copenhagen, Herlev, Denmark
Borgmester Ib Juuls Vej 83, 2730 Herlev, Denmark

^m Department of Clinical Biochemistry, Copenhagen University Hospital – Rigshospitalet,
Blegdamsvej 9, 2100 Copenhagen, DENMARK

*denotes equal contribution

Type of manuscript: Clinical Research Article
Trial registration: ClinicalTrials.gov, identifier: NCT0203645

Corresponding author:

Søren Zöga Diederichsen, MD, PhD
Department of Cardiology, Copenhagen University Hospital - Rigshospitalet
Inge Lehmanns Vej 7, 2100 Copenhagen, DENMARK
Mail: soeren.zoega.diederichsen@regionh.dk
Cell: +45 2345 0489
X/Twitter: @SZDiederichsen
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9687-0857>

Tables	3
Table S1. AF detection in TSH tertiles.....	3
Table S2. AF burden in the ILR group.....	3
Table S3. AF detection in subgroups based on randomization arm	3
Figures	4
Figure S1 - Distribution of TSH.....	4
Figure S2 – Cumulative incidences of AF diagnosis and OAC initiation according to randomization arm	5
Figure S3 – Cumulative incidence of AF episodes lasting 24 hours or longer in the ILR group according to TSH	6
Figure S4 – Cumulative incidence of secondary clinical outcomes according to TSH.....	7
Figure S5 – Percentage of participants experiencing AF symptoms	8
Figure S6 – Cumulative incidence of AF diagnosis according to TSH excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or with abnormal TSH (reference range 0.3-4.0 mIU/L).....	9
Figure S7 – Cumulative incidences of AF episodes lasting 24 hours or longer in the ILR group according to TSH tertiles excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or with abnormal TSH (reference range 0.3-4.0 mIU/L).....	10
Figure S8 – Cumulative incidence of secondary clinical outcomes according to randomization arm grouped by TSH tertile	11
Figure S9 – Cumulative incidence of the primary outcome in females according to randomization arm grouped by TSH tertile and hazard ratios according to continuous TSH	13
Figure S10 – Cumulative incidence of the primary outcome in males according to randomization arm grouped by TSH tertile and hazard ratios according to continuous TSH	14
Figure S11 – Cumulative incidence of primary and secondary clinical outcomes according to TSH excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or with abnormal TSH (reference range 0.3-4.0 mIU/L).....	15
Figure S12 – Cumulative incidence of primary and secondary clinical outcomes according to randomization arm grouped by TSH tertile excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or with abnormal TSH (reference range 0.3-4.0 mIU/L).....	16
Figure S13 – Effect of ILR screening vs usual care on primary and secondary outcomes according to continuous TSH excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or with abnormal TSH (reference range 0.3-4.0 mIU/L).....	18

Tables

Table S1. AF detection in TSH tertiles

	T1 (N=2011)		T2 (N=1997)		T3 (N=1995)	
	ILR (N=498)	Usual care (N=1513)	ILR (N=474)	Usual care (N=1523)	ILR (N=528)	Usual care (N=1467)
AF diagnosis	153 (31%)	180 (12%)	162 (34%)	183 (12%)	161 (30%)	187 (13%)
Device-detected AF ≥ 24 hours	35 (7%)	-	24 (5%)	-	28 (5%)	-

Values are presented as n (%).

T1 (TSH ≤1.20 mIU/L), T2 (TSH 1.21-1.92 mIU/L), T3 (TSH>1.92 mIU/L).

Abbreviations: AF, atrial fibrillation; ILR, implantable loop recorder.

Table S2. AF burden in the ILR group

	ILR			
	T1	T2	T3	p-value ¹
AF burden, [%]	0.15 (0.05– 0.94)	0.19 (0.05– 0.76)	0.18 (0.04– 0.77)	0.90

¹ Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

Values are presented as median (interquartile range).

T1 (TSH ≤1.20 mIU/L), T2 (TSH 1.21-1.92 mIU/L), T3 (TSH>1.92 mIU/L).

Abbreviations: AF, atrial fibrillation; ILR, implantable loop recorder.

Table S3. AF detection in subgroups based on randomization arm

	TSH below lower reference (N=123)		TSH above upper reference (N=251)		Antithyroid medication (N=36)		Hypothyroid medication (N=380)	
	ILR (N=27)	Usual care (N=96)	ILR (N=63)	Usual care (N=188)	ILR (N=5)	Usual care (N=31)	ILR (N=98)	Usual care (N=282)
AF diagnosis	6 (22%)	11 (11%)	22 (35%)	25 (13%)	1 (20%)	4 (13%)	25 (26%)	31 (11%)
Device-detected AF ≥ 24 hours	1 (4%)	-	3 (5%)	-	0 (0%)	-	3 (3%)	-

Values are presented as n(%).

T1 (TSH ≤1.20 mIU/L), T2 (TSH 1.21-1.92 mIU/L), T3 (TSH>1.92 mIU/L).

Abbreviations: AF, atrial fibrillation; ILR, implantable loop recorder; TSH, Thyroid stimulating hormone.

Figures

The baseline distribution of TSH and the tertiles are displayed. The reference range for TSH (0.3-4.0 mIU/L) is illustrated by dashed lines.
 T1 (TSH ≤1.20 mIU/L), T2 (TSH 1.21-1.92 mIU/L), T3 (TSH>1.92 mIU/L).
 Abbreviations: TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Figure S2 – Cumulative incidences of AF diagnosis and OAC initiation according to randomization arm

Time-to-first-event curves for AF diagnosis (above panels) and OAC initiation (below panels) according to randomization arms are displayed.

Adjusted p for interaction between TSH tertiles and randomization arms:

AF diagnosis: p-value=0.44.

OAC initiation: p-value=0.50.

Benjamini-Hochberg corrected p for interaction:

AF diagnosis: p-value=0.67.

OAC initiation: p-value=0.67.

Interaction terms and aHRs were adjusted for baseline age, sex, body mass index, alcohol consumption, smoking pack years, cholesterol level, RAS blockers, and history of hypertension, diabetes, stroke, heart failure, valvular heart disease, acute myocardial infarction, and thyrotoxicosis.

T1 (TSH ≤1.20 mIU/L), T2 (TSH 1.21-1.92 mIU/L), T3 (TSH >1.92 mIU/L).

Abbreviations: AF, atrial fibrillation; aHR, adjusted hazard ratio; CI, confidence interval; ILR, implantable loop recorder, OAC, oral anticoagulation; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Figure S3 – Cumulative incidence of AF episodes lasting 24 hours or longer in the ILR group according to TSH

Figure S6 – Cumulative incidence of AF diagnosis according to TSH excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or with abnormal TSH (reference range 0.3-4.0 mIU/L)

Time-to-first-event curves for AF diagnosis according to TSH tertiles excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or outside the reference range are displayed. AHRs were adjusted for baseline age, sex, body mass index, alcohol consumption, smoking pack years, cholesterol level, RAS blockers, and history of hypertension, diabetes, stroke, heart failure, valvular heart disease, acute myocardial infarction, and thyrotoxicosis (with T1 as reference).

T1 (TSH ≤1.20 mIU/L), T2 (TSH 1.21-1.92 mIU/L), T3 (TSH >1.92 mIU/L).

Abbreviations: AF, atrial fibrillation; aHR, adjusted hazard ratio; CI, confidence interval; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Figure S7 – Cumulative incidences of AF episodes lasting 24 hours or longer in the ILR group according to TSH tertiles excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or with abnormal TSH (reference range 0.3-4.0 mIU/L)

Time-to-first-event curves for AF episodes lasting 24 hours or longer in the ILR group according to TSH tertiles excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or outside the reference range are displayed. AHRs were adjusted for baseline age, sex, body mass index, alcohol consumption, smoking pack years, cholesterol level, RAS blockers, and history of hypertension, diabetes, stroke, heart failure, valvular heart disease, acute myocardial infarction, and thyrotoxicosis (with T1 as reference).

T1 (TSH ≤1.20 mIU/L), T2 (TSH 1.21-1.92 mIU/L), T3 (TSH >1.92 mIU/L).

Abbreviations: AF, atrial fibrillation; aHR, adjusted hazard ratio; CI, confidence interval; ILR, implantable loop recorder; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Figure S8 – Cumulative incidence of secondary clinical outcomes according to randomization arm grouped by TSH tertile

Adjusted p for interaction between TSH tertile and randomization arm:
p-value=0.01

Benjamini-Hochberg corrected p for interaction:
p-value=0.11

Adjusted p for interaction between TSH tertile and randomization arm:
p-value=0.42

Benjamini-Hochberg corrected p for interaction:
p-value=0.67

Adjusted p for interaction between TSH tertile and randomization arm:
p-value=0.19

Benjamini-Hochberg corrected p for interaction:
p-value=0.51

Adjusted p for interaction between TSH tertile and randomization arm:
p-value=0.76

Benjamini-Hochberg corrected p for interaction:
p-value=0.76

Adjusted p for interaction between TSH tertile and randomization arm:
p-value=0.69

Benjamini-Hochberg corrected p for interaction:
p-value=0.76

Time-to-first-event curves for secondary clinical outcomes according to randomization arms grouped by TSH tertiles are displayed. Interaction terms and aHRs were adjusted for baseline age, sex, body mass index, alcohol consumption, smoking pack years, cholesterol level, RAS blockers, and history of hypertension, diabetes, stroke, heart failure, valvular heart disease, acute myocardial infarction, and thyrotoxicosis. Interaction terms were calculated according to TSH tertile values.

T1 (TSH ≤1.20 mIU/L), T2 (TSH 1.21-1.92 mIU/L), T3 (TSH >1.92 mIU/L).

Abbreviations: AF, atrial fibrillation; aHR, adjusted hazard ratio; CI, confidence interval; ILR, implantable loop recorder; SE, systemic embolism; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Figure S9 – Cumulative incidence of the primary outcome in females according to randomization arm grouped by TSH tertile and hazard ratios according to continuous TSH

Adjusted p for interaction between TSH tertile and randomization arm:
p-value=0.02

Time-to-first-event curves for the primary clinical outcome according to randomization arms grouped by TSH tertiles in females (above panels). Interaction terms and aHRs were adjusted for baseline age, body mass index, alcohol consumption, smoking pack years, cholesterol level, RAS blockers, and history of hypertension, diabetes, stroke, heart failure, valvular heart disease, acute myocardial infarction, and thyrotoxicosis. Interaction terms were calculated according to TSH tertile values.

HRs for the effects of randomization arms in females are presented with TSH modeled as a continuous variable (below panels).

T1 (TSH ≤ 1.20 mIU/L), T2 (TSH 1.21-1.92 mIU/L), T3 (TSH > 1.92 mIU/L).

Abbreviations: AHR, adjusted hazard ratio; ILR, implantable loop recorder; SE, systemic embolism; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Figure S10 – Cumulative incidence of the primary outcome in males according to randomization arm grouped by TSH tertile and hazard ratios according to continuous TSH

Adjusted p for interaction between TSH tertile and randomization arm:
p-value=0.43

Time-to-first-event curves for the primary clinical outcome according to randomization arms grouped by TSH tertiles in males (above panels). Interaction terms and aHRs were adjusted for baseline age, body mass index, alcohol consumption, smoking pack years, cholesterol level, RAS blockers, and history of hypertension, diabetes, stroke, heart failure, valvular heart disease, acute myocardial infarction, and thyrotoxicosis. Interaction terms were calculated according to TSH tertile values.

HRs for the effects of randomization arms in males are presented with TSH modeled as a continuous variable (below panels).

T1 (TSH ≤ 1.20 mIU/L), T2 (TSH 1.21-1.92 mIU/L), T3 (TSH > 1.92 mIU/L).

Abbreviations: AHR, adjusted hazard ratio; ILR, implantable loop recorder; SE, systemic embolism; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Figure S11 – Cumulative incidence of primary and secondary clinical outcomes according to TSH excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or with abnormal TSH (reference range 0.3-4.0 mIU/L)

Time-to-first-event curves for secondary clinical outcomes according to TSH tertiles in the whole population excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or outside the reference range are displayed. AHRs were adjusted for baseline age, sex, body mass index, alcohol consumption, smoking pack years, cholesterol level, RAS blockers, and history of hypertension, diabetes, stroke, heart failure, valvular heart disease, acute myocardial infarction, and thyrotoxicosis (with T1 as reference).
 T1 (TSH ≤1.20 mIU/L), T2 (TSH 1.21-1.92 mIU/L), T3 (TSH>1.92 mIU/L).

Abbreviations: AF, atrial fibrillation; aHR, adjusted hazard ratio; CI, confidence interval; ILR, implantable loop recorder; SE, systemic embolism; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Figure S12 – Cumulative incidence of primary and secondary clinical outcomes according to randomization arm grouped by TSH tertile excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or with abnormal TSH (reference range 0.3-4.0 mIU/L)

Adjusted p for interaction between TSH tertile and randomization arm:
p-value=0.51

Adjusted p for interaction between TSH tertile and randomization arm:
p-value=0.86

Adjusted p for interaction between TSH tertile and randomization arm:
p-value=0.54

Time-to-first-event curves for secondary clinical outcomes according to randomization arms grouped by TSH tertiles excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or outside the reference range are displayed. Interaction terms and aHRs were adjusted for baseline age, sex, body mass index, alcohol consumption, smoking pack years, cholesterol level, RAS blockers, and history of hypertension, diabetes, stroke, heart failure, valvular heart disease, acute myocardial infarction, and thyrotoxicosis. Interaction terms were calculated according to TSH tertile values.

T1 (TSH ≤ 1.20 mIU/L), T2 (TSH 1.21-1.92 mIU/L), T3 (TSH > 1.92 mIU/L).
 Abbreviations: AF, atrial fibrillation; aHR, adjusted hazard ratio; CI, confidence interval; ILR, implantable loop recorder; SE, systemic embolism; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Figure S13 – Effect of ILR screening vs usual care on primary and secondary outcomes according to continuous TSH excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or with abnormal TSH (reference range 0.3-4.0 mIU/L)

HRs for the effects of randomization arms are presented with TSH modeled as a continuous variable excluding participants treated with thyroid hormone replacement or antithyroid agents or outside the reference range are displayed.
 P for interaction between continuous TSH and randomization arm:
 Stroke or SE: p-value=0.01
 Stroke, SE or cardiovascular death: p-value=0.01
 All-cause death: p-value=0.76

Abbreviations: ILR, implantable loop recorder; HR, hazard ratio; SE, systemic embolism; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.